

ISic3671

I.Sicily inscription 3671

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 885

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus)
2. Accaeae Calliope
3. Q(uintus) Rupilius Onesi
4. mus coiugi
5. bene de se
6. meritae

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

Sacred to the shades of the underworld. Accaea Calliope. Quintus Rupilius Onesimus, her partner, [built this] for her good merits

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 123023

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.1088*.5 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 244

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